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**ONSET CLUSTERS AND ELICITED EPENTHETIC VOWELS IN SPOKEN
ENGLISH OF SELECTED HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN RINGIM, JIGAWA
STATE, NIGERIA**

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Abstract

This study investigates onset cluster simplification through vowel epenthesis in the spoken English of Senior Secondary School students in Ringim Local Government Area, Jigawa State, Nigeria, within the framework of Prince and Smolensky's Optimality Theory. A qualitative research design was employed for the analysis, complemented by quantitative approach employed to identify frequency patterns. The population comprised sixty students, who are Hausa natives, selected from one privately-sponsored and five government-funded senior secondary schools through purposive sampling based on the strength of gender balance and communicative competence. Data were elicited through oral reading tasks consisting of 152 lexical items with onset consonant clusters, organised into four groups according to vowel nuclei (/a/, /ai/, /ɛ/, /e/, /i/, /o/, /ɔ/, /u/). Reading sessions were audio-recorded with a smart cell phone device, and transcribed using phonetic transcription in line with the IPA, i-Chart 2025. The findings of the study reveal that vowel epenthesis in onset clusters is primarily conditioned by vowel harmony, particularly Advanced Tongue Root (ATR) and front/back alignment, and secondarily by consonantal coarticulation effects. Four high vowels, [ɔ], [ɪ], [u], and [i], were identified as the principal epenthetic segments. The epenthetic vowels demonstrate predictable patterns in relation to surrounding segmental features. However, consonantal properties such as labiality, rhoticity, and frication do override harmonic expectations. The results highlight a two-tier conditioning system in epenthetic vowel selection. This reflects the influence of Hausa phonotactic constraints on Hausa variety of Nigerian English. Framed within World Englishes, the research contributes to understanding regional variation in Nigerian English and its implications for multilingual education.

Keywords: consonant cluster, vowel harmony, vowel epenthesis, educated Hausa English, cluster simplification strategy

Introduction

English, as a global language, has diversified into localized forms shaped by sociolinguistic and cultural influences (Crystal, 2003). This development underpins the concept of World Englishes (Kachru, 1985; Kirkpatrick, 2014), which recognizes multiple legitimate varieties beyond native-speaker norms. Nigerian English, a prominent African variety, exhibits several regional and social sub-varieties influenced by the country's linguistic diversity (Banjo, 1971; Jowitt, 2019; Jubril, 1982). In Nigeria, where English functions as the official language and medium of instructions, its use is shaped by the phonological and syntactic systems of local languages (Adegbite, 2010; Jowitt, 2019). A notable feature, particularly in Northern Nigeria, is the simplification of consonant clusters through vowel epenthesis, reflecting not incompetence but a regional phonological identity (Bamgbose, 1998; Olajide & Olaniyi, 2013). In Hausa-dominated areas like Ringim, vowel epenthesis in students' spoken English is observed as both a learning strategy and a marker of localized English use. This has been attributed to Hausa phonotactics, which typically avoid consonant clusters (Aliyu, 2024; Sani, 2005).

Of course, Nigerian English is a recognized national variety of World Englishes and much has been written on its lexical and syntactic features. However, more research efforts are still required, especially as it concerns its regional phonological features to facilitate the codification of Nigerian English pronunciation dictionary (Soneye, 2021). This study therefore argues that vowel epenthesis in the English of secondary school students in Ringim offers insights into northern Nigerian English accent, as the analysis of the patterns of vowel insertion among the students reveals some idiosyncratic features of Hausa English accent that will be useful in the codification process of the Hausa English accent. Of course, documenting such features is essential for linguistic scholarship and for informing language education policies that incorporate local realities.

This study therefore examines vowel epenthesis as a strategy for consonant cluster simplification among Senior Secondary School students in Ringim Local Government Area (henceforth LGA), Jigawa State. The LGA, within the Ringim Emirate and Hadejia-Jama'are River Basin, is predominantly Hausa-speaking and Muslim. It is observed that epenthesis in their spoken English is systematic rather than arbitrary, influenced by syllable structures, cluster compositions, and nucleus types. The study's objective is to analyse how these factors determine the insertion of particular vowels in English words, thereby testing the hypothesis that vowel epenthesis is rule-governed.

The Hausa Syllable Structure

Hausa has three permissible and possible syllable structures as identified by most researchers (e.g., Jaggar, 2001 and Caron, 2013). Examples of these structures are as follows:

- | | | |
|------------------------|--------------------------|-------------------------|
| a. Kaa.re (dog) CV | b. Sha.re (sweep) CV.CV | c. Faa.do (fall) CVV.CV |
| d. Zau.na (sit) CVV.CV | e. Dau.ko (bring) CVV.CV | f. Can (there) CVC |

According to (Sani, 2005), basically, a syllable is of two structural types. These are open and closed syllables. An open syllable is composed of a consonant followed by a vowel which, in Hausa, can be long, short or a diphthong. It is represented as CV/CVV. A closed syllable, on the other hand is made up of a consonant followed by a short vowel and another consonant respectively. It is represented as CVC. In both types of syllables, the first consonant is technically known as the onset, the following as the nucleus or syllabic consonant and the final consonant in the case of a closed syllable as the coda. Examples are below:

- | | | |
|-------------------|-------------------------|------------------------|
| a. Ci CV (eat) | b. Waje CV-CV (outside) | c. Jii CVV (hearing) |
| d. Kai CVV (head) | e. Yau CVV (today) | f. Biyar CV-CVC (five) |
| g. Nan CVC (here) | | |

Furthermore, just as outrightly mentioned, Hausa has only three syllable types: CV, CVV (where VV can be a long vowel or a diphthong) and CVC. In a few instances, a syllabic nasal

serves as the vocalic nucleus of a syllable or as a syllable by itself, e.g., ngulu or ‘ngulu =ungulu ‘vulture’. The CV syllable type is light; the other two are heavy. Syllable may not contain both a long vowel (monophthongal or diphthongal) and a final consonant. Such over heavy syllables, which commonly result from morphological processes, are automatically pared down by nucleus reduction rules, e.g., *râi-n-sa (life –of-him) → rânsà ‘his life’; faar-koo →farkoo ‘beginning’ Cuus-cuusaa → cuccuusaa ‘stuff repeatedly’. This syllable structures show that Hausa does not permit consonant clusters as onsets and codas as obtainable in English; hence the reason for the incidence of vowel insertion in Hausa spoken English.

Previous Studies on Epenthesis in Nigerian English

Idiatov (2017) examines the insertion of an alveolar coronal stop [t] or fricative [s] after another alveolar coronal pre-pausally and phrase-internally by Bena L1 speakers. The study also compares word-final consonant epenthesis in other English varieties, outlining how they differ in execution. Focusing on consonant epenthesis, it contrasts with the present study, which examines vowel epenthesis as a cluster simplification strategy. Ajileye, Famoriji, and Akinyelu (2023) investigate the form, pattern, and diversity of vowel epenthesis in Yoruba loanwords, identifying its functions in adapting borrowed words. They classify epenthetic vowels by nature, function, and position, and explore causes and quality. While their objectives align with the present study, their focus is Yoruba loanwords, whereas the current study analyses English words by Hausa-speaking students in Ringim LGA. Benjamin-Ohwodede and Osewa (2023) analyse assimilation, apocope, and epenthesis in Nigerian English-based pidgin using Optimality Theory. They explain how faithfulness and markedness constraints interact to produce these processes. Although both studies employ a similar theoretical framework, the study centres on pidgin English, while the current research targets educated Hausa English. Unegbu (2025) studies phonotactic repair strategies, vowel epenthesis and consonant deletion, used by Igbo L2 English speakers to address disallowed consonant clusters in Igbo syllable

structure. Using Contrastive Analysis Hypothesis and Markedness Differential Hypothesis, ten speakers' readings were analysed with auditory and Praat methods. Findings show /a/ and /k/ as the most marked in epenthesis and deletion, respectively. The study views these processes not solely as errors but as articulation aids, a perspective shared with the current research on Hausa English.

Theoretical Framework

Optimality Theory (henceforth, OT), developed by Prince and Smolensky (1993), is adopted for this study because it explains how phonological processes, including vowel epenthesis, are shaped by ranked, violable constraints to produce optimal outputs. OT is a constraint-based model that accounts for grammatical regularities by showing how input forms (underlying representations) are transformed into surface forms through the interaction of constraints. Its goal is to determine the most harmonic output that best satisfies a hierarchy of constraints. Structural regularities are found in output forms, not input configurations (Prince & Smolensky, 2004).

OT holds that Universal Grammar consists of constraints on well-formedness: markedness constraints, which require outputs to meet certain structural conditions, and faithfulness constraints, which preserve input features in the output. These constraints often conflict (satisfying one may violate another), making ranking essential. The OT architecture has three universal components: the Generator (Gen), which produces candidate outputs; the Constraint set (Con), which lists possible constraints; and the Evaluator (Eval), which selects the most optimal form based on strict ranking. In strict domination, violating a higher-ranked constraint cannot be offset by satisfying lower-ranked ones. Evaluation uses *violation marks* in tableaux to show conflicts, with symbols such as “*” for a violation, “!” for fatal violation, and “→” marking the winner.

Faithfulness constraints include DEP (no insertions), MAX (no deletions), IDENT [feature] (no feature changes), Linearity (no metathesis), Uniformity (no fusion), and Integrity (no vowel breaking). Markedness constraints relevant to this study include *Complex (no consonant clusters), ONSET (syllables must have onsets), NoCoda (no final consonants), and AGREE (adjacent segments must agree in voicing/place). In analysing vowel epenthesis, these constraints will help explain how Hausa-English speakers resolve cluster simplification while balancing markedness pressures and faithfulness to input.

It is noted that constraints in OT are quite numerous; about 1666 of them have been identified, documented and catalogued (google constraints_catalog.xls) by Ashley, *et al.* (2010). Ashley *et al.* gathered these constraints from the inception of OT to the period of 2008, and have classified them into six main groups/ types each having subtypes based on the nature of the constraints, whether it is about features, phonotactics, morphology, etc. The six broad groups are Alignment, Antifaithfulness, Faithfulness, Local conjunction, Markedness, and Other/Miscellaneous. Two of these constraints' typologies (Faithfulness and Markedness) are found relevant to the analysis of data in this study, particularly the featural constraints of these typologies. Some of these, after adaptation, guide our analysis, especially those culled from Coetzee (2006); for example: Max[+back] = every occurrence of [+back] in the input has a correspondent in the output

Methodology

This study adopts a descriptive qualitative research design to investigate vowel epenthesis as a consonant cluster simplification strategy in students' spoken English. The qualitative aspect enabled detailed phonological analysis. The population comprised sixty (60) Senior Secondary School students from one privately sponsored and five government-funded schools in Ringim Local Government Area, Jigawa State, Nigeria. The choice of one privately sponsored secondary school was informed by the observation that other non-government sponsored

schools operate only the primary and junior secondary sections. Using purposive sampling, ten senior secondary students (five each from SSS 2 and SSS 3) that are Hausa natives were selected from each school, while ensuring gender balance and adequate communicative competence in English. Data were collected through oral reading tasks designed to elicit controlled speech. A list of 152 lexical items containing consonant clusters (primarily in word-initial position) was divided into four groups based on vowel nuclei: Group 1 (/a/, /ai/), Group 2 (/ɛ/, /e/), Group 3 (/i/, /o/), and Group 4 (/ɔ/, /u/). Each participant completed four reading sessions lasting 10–15 minutes. All sessions were audio-recorded using a mobile phone recorder, with ethical clearance and informed consent obtained from relevant authorities, parents, and participants. Recordings were perceptually transcribed using narrow phonetic transcription (IPA, i-Chart 2023) to identify and analyse vowel epenthesis and related phonological features. The analyses are presented in tables followed by detailed explanations of findings.

Analysis

Four epenthetic vowels have been identified in the reading performances of the study participants. The syllable structures (consisting of onset consonant clusters and vowel nuclei) and the type of epenthetic vowel they elicited from the participants while trying to simplify the clusters are presented and analysed as identified in this section. The presentation is done in rejigged tableaux and tables which show the constraints preferred by the speakers, the number of speakers that favoured a particular constraint in their readings, the structures, lexical examples and lexical items (as exceptions) in which the epenthetic vowel does not occur, and then followed by detailed explanations of the contents of the tables. In the tableaux, Max (CLUS) is used for the constraint: maximise clusters (which means that the cluster should be maintained); INS (NBC) stands for insert back near close vowel /ʊ/; INS (NFC) for insert front near close vowel /ɪ/; INS (BC) for insert back close vowel /u/; INS (FC) for insert front close

vowel /i/; and NOP for number of participants that preferred a particular constraint or realisation. .

i. Cluster Patterns and Syllabic Nucleus Attracting Epenthetic [ʊ]

The syllabic structures attracting epenthetic [ʊ] in the participants’ articulation of onset clusters are presented below in Tableau 1 and Table 1.

Tableau 1: Structures Attracting Constraint INST(NBC) [ʊ] and their Frequency

S/N	Structure	Syllabic Realisations/ Candidates	Constraints			NOP
			INS (NBC)	Max (CLUS)	INS (NFC)	
1	C+l+(/ɔ/)	☞ [Cɔɫ-]		*	*!	52
2	C+r+(/a, au, ai, ε, εə, ɔ)	☞ [Cɔr a, au, ai, ε, εə, ɔ]		*	*!	52
3	s+C+(/ɔ/)	☞ [sɔCɔ-]		*	*!	52
4	C+w+(/a, au, ε/)	☞ [Cɔw a, au, ε-]		*	*!	52
5	s+C+r+(/ε, ɔ/)	☞ [sɔCɔrε/ɔ-]		*	*!	52

Tableau 1 shows that out of the sixty participants selected for the study, fifty-two preferred to insert near back close vowel [ʊ] to simply clusters in the following syllabic structures: C+l+(/ɔ/), C+r+(/a, au, ai, ε, εə, ɔ), s+C+(/ɔ/), C+w+(/a, au, ε/), and s+C+r+(/ε, ɔ/). However, there are exceptions in their articulation of structures 2 and 4. These are shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Syllabic Structures Attracting Epenthetic [ʊ] with Examples and Exceptions

Syllabic Structures	Lexical Examples	Exceptions and NoP
C+l+(/ɔ/)	<i>flop, plot, blob, flaw, plum</i>	-

C+r+(/a, au, ai, ε, εə, ə)	<i>crab, crown, fly, shred, trot</i>	<i>shrank</i> [ʃɪrə-] (49), <i>bread</i> [bɪrə-] (52)
s+C+(/ə/)	<i>score, scum, snub, spot</i>	-
C+w+(/a, au, ε/)	<i>dwarf, dwell, twerk, twang</i>	<i>twenty</i> [tuwe-] (52)
s+C+r+(/ε, ə/)	<i>spread, scrub, strut, strong</i>	-

Table 1 shows the syllabic patterns that condition the insertion of the epenthetic vowel [ʊ] in the participants' speech. The analysis reveals that vowel harmony, especially the Advanced Tongue Root (ATR) feature, and consonantal influence are central in the selection of [ʊ]. In C+l+(/ə/) structure, insertion of [ʊ] occurs consistently because both are back and -ATR, reflecting vowel harmony. For C+r+(/a, au, ai, ε, εə, ə/), [ʊ] aligns with ATR harmony, but front vowels such as /a/ and /ε/ create complexity. The choice of [ʊ] instead of [ɪ] is linked to the retraction effect of /r/, although in *shrank* most participants (forty-nine) inserted [ɪ], likely influenced by the fronting effect of /ʃ/.

In *bread*, participants inserted [u], an +ATR vowel, because /ε/ was reinterpreted as /e/, maintaining harmony. In s+C+(/ə/) structure, insertion of [ʊ] aligns with both backness and ATR. For C+w+(/a, au, ε/), participants inserted [ʊ] rather than [ɪ]; the labiality and backness of /w/ likely encouraged this choice. An exception was *twenty*, where [u] appeared, also explained by a reinterpretation of /ε/ as /e/. In s+C+r+(/ε, ə/) structure, ATR harmony accounts for [ʊ], though in *spread* the bilabial plosive /p/ may have influenced backness, giving forms like [sɒpʊrəd]. In conclusion, the data show ATR harmony as the dominant factor in epenthetic vowel choice, with consonantal context, particularly labiality and backness, also exerting strong influence.

ii. Cluster Patterns and Syllabic Nucleus Attracting Epenthetic [ɪ]

The syllabic structures attracting epenthetic [ɪ] in the participants' articulation of onset clusters are presented in Tableau 2 and Table 2 below.

Tableau 2: Structures Attracting Constraint INST(NFC) [ɪ] and their Frequency

S/N	Structure	Syllabic Realisations/ Candidates	Constraints			NOP
			INS (NFC)	Max (CLUS)	INS (NBC)	
1	C+l+(/a, ai/)	☞ [Cɪla, ai-]		*	*!	52
2	s+C+(/a, ai, ε/)	☞ [sɪCa, ai, ε-]		*	*!	49-52
3	s+C+r or l+(/a, au, ai/)	☞ [sɪCɪr a, au, ai-]]		*	*!	52

As can be seen in Tableau 2, participants preferred to insert near front close vowel [ɪ] to simplify the three syllable structures. There are, however, exceptions to their preferences. These exceptions are presented and explained in Table 2.

Table 2: Syllabic Structures Attracting Epenthetic [ɪ] with Examples and Exceptions

Syllabic Structures	Lexical Examples	Exceptions and NoP
C+l+(/a, ai/)	<i>class, slap, clown, glide, fly, slime</i>	<i>black [bɔra-] (52), flag [f/pɔla-] (52), plant [pɔla-] (52), fly [f/pɔla-] (52)</i>
s+C+(/a, ai, ε/)	<i>scan, scare, sky, slime, sly, sled, stir</i>	<i>spam [sɔpa-] (52), swam [sɔwa-] (52), swarm [sɔwa-] (52), smile [sɔmai-] (49), sped [sɔpe-] (52), swell [sɔwe-] (52), smell [sɔme-] (49)</i>

s+C+r or l+(/a, au, ai/)	<i>scram, scribe, stripe</i>	<i>splash [sɒpɒlə-] (52), splat [sɒpɒlə-] (52), sprout [sɒpɒraʊ-] (52), splice [sɒpɒləi-] (52)</i>
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Table 2 presents syllabic structures that attract the insertion of the epenthetic vowel [ɪ]. The main patterns [C+l+(/a, ai/), s+C+(/a, ai, ε/), and s+C+r or l+(/a, au, ai/)] involve nuclei such as /a/, /ai/, and /ε/, which are front and [-ATR]. These features align with [ɪ], also a front [-ATR] vowel, showing that vowel harmony guides epenthetic vowel choice. However, exceptions occur where [ʊ] is inserted instead of [ɪ]. Words like *black, flag, plant, fly, spam, swam, smile* (49 participants), *swell*, and *splash* were realised with [ʊ] by most participants (52 of the participants). This pattern indicates that labial consonants such as /p/, /b/, and /m/ exert coarticulatory influence, favouring back and rounded vowels. The result is a systematic shift from [ɪ] to [ʊ] in the presence of labial onsets. In all, the data suggest that while vowel harmony explains most cases, consonantal environment, particularly labiality, significantly shapes epenthetic vowel selection.

iii. Cluster Patterns and Syllabic Nucleus Attracting Epenthetic [u]

The syllabic structures attracting epenthetic [u] in the participants' articulation of onset clusters are presented Tableau 3 and Table 3 below.

Tableau 3: Structures Attracting Constraint INST(BC) [u] and their Frequency

S/N	Structure	Syllabic Realisations	Constraints			NOP
			INS (BC)	Max (CLUS)	INS (FC)	
1	C+l or r+(/o, u/)	☞ [Cul o, u-]/ [Curo, u-]		*	*!	52
2	C +w+(/i/)	☞ [Cuwi-]		*	*!	52
3	s+C+(/o, u/)	☞ [suCo, u-]		*	*!	52

4	s+C+r or l+(/o, u/)	☞ [suCuro, u-] / [suCulo, u-]		*	*!	52
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In structures 1 to 4 as represented in Tableau 3, the participants preferred to insert back-close vowel [u] to simplify the clusters in the structures. These are properly explained in Table 3.

Table 3: Syllabic Structures Attracting Epenthetic [u] with Examples and Exceptions

Syllabic Structures	Lexical Examples	Exceptions and NoP
C+l or r+(/o, u/)	<i>clove, glow, slow, blow, globe, blue, glue</i>	-
C +w+(/i/)	<i>dwindle, tweed, twist, twinkle, tweak, twig</i>	-
s+C+(/o, u/)	<i>smoke, snow, skew, swoosh, swoop</i>	-
s+C+r or l+(/o, u/)	<i>screw, spruce, scroll</i>	-

Table 3 shows the syllabic structures that attract the insertion of the epenthetic vowel [u]. These environments involve nuclei such as /o/ and /u/, which are [+ATR] and back vowels. Participants consistently inserted [u], which shares these features, reflecting vowel harmony and assimilation. A notable exception occurs in C+w+(/i/) structures, as in *dwindle, tweed, twist, twinkle, and tweak*. Although /i/ is a front [+ATR] vowel, participants still inserted [u]. This mismatch is explained by the coarticulatory influence of /w/, a labial glide with back qualities, which overrides the frontness of /i/ and favours a back vowel. The data therefore show that while vowel harmony generally determines [u] insertion, consonantal context, particularly /w/, can significantly alter the expected pattern.

iv. Cluster Patterns and Syllabic Nucleus Attracting Epenthetic [i]

The syllabic structures attracting epenthetic [i] in the participants' articulation of onset clusters are presented in Tableau 4 and Table 4 below.

Tableau 4: Structures Attracting Constraint INST (FC) [i] and their Frequency

S/N	Structure	Syllabic Realisations	Constraints			NOP
			INS (FC)	Max (CLUS)	INS (BC)	
1	C+l or r+(/e, i/)	☞ [Cile, i-]/ [Cire, i-]		*	*!	52
2	s+C+(/e, i/)	☞ [siCe, i-]		*	*!	52
3	s+C+r or l+(/i/)	☞ [siCiri-]/ [siCiri-]		*	*!	52

As shown in Tableau 4, participants preferred to insert front close vowel [i] to simplify the three syllable structures. There are, however, exceptions to their preferences. These exceptions are presented and explained in Table 4:

Table 4: Syllabic Structures Attracting Epenthetic [i] with Examples and Exceptions

Syllabic Structures	Lexical Examples	Exceptions and NoP
C+l or r+(/e, i/)	<i>slay, clay, cling, fling, slip,</i> <i>sleep</i>	<i>play [pule-] (52), braid [bure-] (52), frame [fure-] (52), trade [ture-] (52), tray [ture-] (52)</i>
s+C+(/e, i/)	<i>stay, skin, skip, sneak, snip</i>	<i>spin [supi-] (52), sweet [suwi-] (52), swing [suwi-] (52), swim [suwi-] (52)</i>
s+C+r or l+(/i/)	<i>stream</i>	<i>split [supili-] (52), splint [supili-] (52), spring [supiri-] (52)</i>

Table 4 presents the syllabic structures that attract the epenthetic vowel [i], largely influenced by vocalic features. The nucleus vowels /e/ and /i/ are [+ATR] and front vowels, and participants inserted [i] with matching features, showing a preference for vowel harmony and smooth articulation. Exceptions arise where [u] is inserted instead of [i], even with front

[+ATR] nuclei. Words such as *play*, *braid*, *frame*, *trade*, *tray*, *spin*, *sweet*, *swing*, *swim*, *split*, *splint*, and *spring* reveal that consonantal context also shapes vowel choice. In *play*, *braid*, and *frame*, labial consonants appear to trigger [u] through labialising influence. In *trade* and *tray*, the liquid /r/ favours a back vowel due to its retracted articulation. Similarly, in *spin*, *sweet*, *swing*, and *swim*, the presence of /p/, /w/, and /m/ encourages [u]. Thus, while front [+ATR] nuclei generally attract [i], consonantal influences, particularly labials and rhotics, can override vowel harmony and lead to [u] insertion. This demonstrates the interplay between vowel and consonantal features in determining epenthesis patterns.

6. Findings

The study investigates epenthetic vowel patterns among Senior Secondary School students in Ringim LGA when simplifying onset clusters. Results show that vowel epenthesis is largely governed by vowel harmony, especially Advanced Tongue Root (ATR) features, but consonantal coarticulation also plays a strong role. The insertion of [ʊ] was dominant before back, [-ATR] vowels, as in C+l+(/ɔ/) and s+C+(/ɔ/), though consonantal context often altered this pattern. Front vowels preceded by /r/ sometimes attracted [ʊ] instead of [i] due to rhotic retraction, while /f/ occasionally favoured [i] through its fronting effect. Labials and the glide /w/ also strongly encouraged [ʊ] regardless of nucleus frontness. The vowel [i] was inserted before front, [-ATR] nuclei such as /a/, /ai/, and /ɛ/, in line with harmonic principles, but labials often shifted this to [ʊ]. The insertion of [u] occurred with [+ATR] back vowels like /o/ and /u/, although /w/ before a front [+ATR] vowel sometimes produced [u] instead of [i]. For [i], harmony with [+ATR] front vowels such as /e/ and /i/ was mostly preserved, yet labials and rhotics often pulled the choice toward [u]. In all, vowel harmony provides the primary conditioning system, while consonantal features such as labiality, rhoticity, and frication act as strong secondary forces that can override harmonic predictions.

7. Conclusion

This study examined vowel epenthesis as a strategy for consonant cluster simplification in the spoken English of Senior Secondary School students in Ringim Local Government Area, Jigawa State, within the framework of Optimality Theory. The analysis revealed that epenthetic vowel selection is primarily governed by vowel harmony, particularly in relation to Advanced Tongue Root features, and secondarily influenced by consonantal factors such as labiality, rhoticity, and frication, which can override harmonic predictions. These findings highlight the interaction between segmental phonology and articulatory phonetics in learners' interlanguage. The study contributes to understanding phonological adaptation among Nigerian learners of English and suggests avenues for further research involving spontaneous speech, cross-dialectal analysis, and longitudinal studies.

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